

Work on Myth: Goethe's *Iphigenia in Tauris*

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Note on Verse Translations

The translated quotations in verse are taken from Ulrich Klingmann, *Kleines Buch zu Goethes "Iphigenie auf Tauris"* (Frankfurt/Main: R.G. Fischer Verlag, 2022). This abridged text provides a parallel modern English verse translation. Additional verse translations are by the author.

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Indeed the gods, whose wisdom mortals envy,
Deceive us, much like fleeting and elusive dreams.
In all that passes, be it human or divine,
Great confusion reigns.

—Euripides, *Iphigenia in Tauris*

The Curse of Myth

If we turn our gaze to the bloody atrocities of the twentieth century and the present, there is much to support the conviction that human actions even today are still subject to the curse which in Goethe's *Iphigenia in Tauris* fatally weighs upon the descendants of the mythical Tantalus. Yet

is there or was there ever a sense in which our actions can be considered curse-determined, and would Goethe have succeeded in breaking such a curse? The play takes as its theme the confused thinking and the bloody deeds of humanity. It seems to me that in times of revolutionary change and the accompanying ideological upheavals, it should be read as a critical *Problemstück* (problem-play) confronting us with the issues of our day.

What is relevant in Goethe's treatment of the Tantalid myth is the engagement with the mythic-theistic order as a problematic system of consciousness. In this context, the image and concept of the "curse" are of central importance, for the curse describes the actions and fate of the youngest representatives of the Tantalid line as *fremdbestimmt*, determined by external forces. Thus, in the expository second scene of the first act, Iphigenia laments to Arkas that "an unknown curse" had weighed upon her since her "earliest youth"; and in the following scene, she reveals the full extent of this *Fremdbestimmung* to Thoas by tracing all subsequent atrocities back to the curse of Jupiter *in illo tempore*:

But the god struck them, marking their brow.
He hid restraint and wisdom, sense and
Judgement from their dark and furtive eyes.
All their desires turned to fury
Which once unleashed, knew no restraint. (330–35)¹

These verses summarize the situation and behavior of the Tantalids. In so doing, the metaphorical description of mental and psychological compulsion provides a twofold explanation for their actions: the god "forged a brazen band around their brow" (literal translation of line 330), and he hid counsel, moderation, wisdom, and patience from their sight. This explanation is clearly not to be taken literally, yet for Iphigenia it holds a real meaning, insofar as the "fury" of the Tantalids is traced back to the mythical will of the god, and, as reflected in her words, there is a causal link between external determination and human action.

The central concern of the play, and also a fundamental issue of our time, is the termination of the destructive and oppressive actions of the House of Tantalus, and more broadly, of humankind. Since human action in Goethe's portrayal is conditioned by the hatred of the gods—"Alas, the hatred of the gods touched all / The members of his race!" (326)—we must ask, within the framework of Goethe's model of reality, where these gods, who heteronomously determine our psychic nature, originate from.

If we follow Hans Blumenberg's² account, the conception of anthropomorphic gods is of an Enlightenment nature. Since the early stages of the development of human consciousness,

¹ The text quotations refer to vol. 5 of the *Hamburg Edition of Goethe's Works* in 14 vols., 9th rev. ed. (Munich: C.H. Beck, 1981).

² Hans Blumenberg, *Arbeit am Mythos*, 4th ed. (Suhrkamp, 1986).

myths and their gods have been products of our imaginative and conceptual faculties.³ In their origin, they represent historical attempts to manage the “terror of reality”⁴ through the medium of consciousness.

From this perspective, the contents of myth are not static but are subject to a *work on myth*—carried out in the process of the effort by human consciousness to orient itself within reality. Myths and the mental configurations they contain were and continue to be further developed, especially through myth-critical, aesthetic mediation.⁵

The anthropomorphically conceived gods were also subject to this process of reimagining and further development.⁶ Their existence has, however, been increasingly called into question since the Enlightenment. Causality is a decisive perception for human consciousness. Once it became apparent that a connection no longer existed between empirical and mythical-metaphysical data, belief in gods and their influence on our fate had to recede or fade away.⁷

Indeed, objectively there are no gods in the sense that they demonstrably determine human fate or that commitment to them could be made obligatory for everyone. While belief in gods has been preserved as a living legacy of myth, there is an important difference between past and present-day belief. This lies essentially in the fact that faith today, in Western pluralistic societies, is understood to be a personal *Bekanntnis* (profession). Today's faith, with its mythical contents, applies only to those who freely profess it and commit themselves to it.

In his treatment of the Tantalus myth in *Iphigenia in Tauris*, Goethe applies modern thinking by using the distinction between subjective and objective validity as the basis for his representation and analysis. From this perspective, the text distinguishes between empirical processes or actions and a mythical understanding, which is characterized as an interpretation of empirical processes. For the recipient of the text, such a depiction raises the question and the problem of what is to be evaluated as empirical and literal within the text's model of reality, and what is not.

It is characteristic of the entire text that the events taken from myth (such as Tantalus's dealings with the gods or Iphigenia's rescue by Diana) are presented in such a way that, from the

³ See Blumenberg, 294: “As certain as it is that myths were invented, even though we know no inventor and no moment of invention, this very lack of knowledge becomes an indication that they must belong to the stock of the very old, and that everything we know is already myth that has entered into reception.”

⁴ Blumenberg, 9: “It means that man did not have the conditions of his existence nearly in his hand and, what is more important, absolutely did not believe them to be in his hand. Sooner or later, he may have interpreted this state of affairs—the overwhelming power of the respective Other—by positing superior powers.”

⁵ Eberhard Jüngel points to the distinction, overlooked by Blumenberg, between a myth-critical and a mythical reception of myth. The mythical reception of a myth belongs to the *work of myth*, in contrast to the mythologizing *work on myth* in the sense of poetization and literary or aesthetic treatment. The waning of a myth's mythical valence would change its function. See Eberhard Jüngel, “Die Wahrheit des Mythos und die Notwendigkeit der Entmythologisierung,” *Hölderlin-Jahrbuch* 27 (1990-1991): 32-50, especially 34-35.

⁶ See Blumenberg, 295: “The *Grenzbegriff* (limit-concept) of work on myth would be to bring it to an end, to venture the most extreme deformation which would allow the genuine figure barely, or almost no longer, to be recognized.”

⁷ See the *Spiegel* Survey “Was glauben die Deutschen?,” *Spiegel* 25 (June 15, 1992): 44: “What was a problem for a few after the Enlightenment has become a problem for many: reconciling faith and reason.”—“For most people, belief in an Almighty is no longer reconcilable with the damage and suffering in this world.”

perspective of the acting characters, they actually took place in the past, yet on the level of the present, they possess no literal reality. Mythic content is effective or present only for the subjective consciousness of the acting characters. In this sense, Goethe's work on myth in *Iphigenia* is to be described as demythologizing,⁸ as he does not carry over the former real actions of gods onto the level of the present, but allows them to stand only as subjective perception and subjective interpretation.

This demythologization characteristic of the text is clearly recognizable in the healing of Orestes. In the play, the events surrounding Orestes are mythically determined by the curse on the House of Tantalus, and the mythically driven action continues with Orestes coming to Tauris under Apollo's instruction to carry out his mission there. In contrast to these mythical plot elements, however, his healing in the present now unfolds *without* empirical divine intervention and *contrary* to the literal wording of Apollo's promise, which stated that the curse would be lifted when he brought "the sister" back to Greece.

Orestes's healing is depicted as a profound shift in consciousness⁹ that transforms his innermost being.¹⁰ In the decisive confrontation with Iphigenia in the third act, he is led by her—"It was your touch that healed me." (2119–20)—to the point where he is ready and able to reorient his consciousness by freeing himself from the delusion¹¹ that the gods want his death¹² and that his sister is compelled by the curse¹³ to murder him. At the height of his despair, he loses consciousness. When Goethe has him come to and speak again, Orestes believes himself to be in the underworld; in his vision of Hades, as an expression of inner reorientation, he sees his ancestors—with the exception of Tantalus—peacefully united.

The concluding scene is brief. To Iphigenia and Pylades, who approach him, Orestes still speaks as if they had descended to accompany him to Pluto's throne. Iphigenia apostrophizes the

⁸ With regard to the various meanings of the term demythologization, see Jünger 44–45.

⁹ See lines 1170–71: "Who are you, whose voice with so much power / Stirs my innermost being?"

¹⁰ In many interpretations, Orestes's guilt is emphasized, which, according to the text, plays no decisive role in the process of "healing"—including the liberation from the curse—and which, in my opinion, should not be stressed as an objective factor if Orestes acted fundamentally due to the curse, insofar as the gods had "chosen" him to be the "slayer" of his mother (lines 707–08). See Heinz Gustav Schmitz, *Kritische Gewaltenteilung* (Suhrkamp, 1988) 72: "A completely conclusive interpretation of the healing has not yet been achieved by any interpreter . . ."—The interpretation by Erika Fischer-Lichte seems essentially correct to me, according to which the healing "takes place with the restoration of authentic interpersonal relationships between the Tantalids." See Erika Fischer-Lichte, "Probleme der Rezeption klassischer Werke—am Beispiel von Goethes Iphigenie," in *Deutsche Literatur zur Zeit der Klassik*, ed. K.O. Conrady (Stuttgart: J.B. Metzlersche Verlagsbuchhandlung, 1977), 129.—The text does not explicitly state that Orestes *atones* for the guilt of matricide through his suffering or his readiness for death. Correspondingly, from this perspective, the Hades vision by no means constitutes "the highest degree of Orestes's self-torment"; see Dieter Borchmeyer, "Iphigenie auf Tauris", in *Interpretationen: Goethes Dramen*, ed. Walter Hinderer (Stuttgart: Reclam Verlag, 1992), 149. Borchmeyer follows Rasch here, who proceeds from the postulate that Orestes "cannot possibly be healed before his guilt, the cause of his illness, has been atoned for and canceled out"; see Wolfdietrich Rasch, *Goethes Iphigenie auf Tauris als Drama der Autonomie* (München: C.H. Beck 1979), 123.

¹¹ Line 1215: "O take delusion from his fixed eye."

¹² Lines 1230–31: "and you I thank, gods, / That I will die without a child to follow on me."

¹³ Lines 1248–49: "The loving sister has / To carry out the deed. I do not blame you; do not weep!"

divine siblings and calls upon Diana not to let her brother “rave in the dark of madness” and to release him “from the curse that binds him.” Then Pylades calls Orestes back to reality. He urges him to take hold of Iphigenia and himself “firmly” and to “listen to his word,” whereupon Orestes, “healed,” turns to Iphigenia with the words:

I feel my heart at last beat freely in
Your arms. (1341–42)

From a mythical perspective, Orestes's healing, in line with Iphigenia's plea to Diana, can be interpreted as a real consequence of mythical-divine intervention, and Orestes takes up the mythical formula of the curse a few verses later with “the curse is lifted” (1358). However, within the framework of the distinctions made in the text, his words are clearly marked as a metaphoric descriptive perception and subjective interpretation of his inner liberation. For the hearer, they imply no mythical-literal content (only Orestes hears the Eumenides):

The curse is lifted, my heart tells me so.
The Eumenides have left for Tartarus,
And I can hear the distant thunder
As the brazen gates fall shut behind them. (1358–61)

The mythical understanding of reality underlying the Tantalid narrative presupposes gods conceived in the image of man as higher beings who interact with humans in human ways. This is evident in the words of Thoas after Iphigenia has revealed her ancestry to him:

Is *he* your ancestor to whom the gods
Gave favour long before our time? Was Tantalus
The one they welcomed to their table and
From whom the gods themselves took counsel? (308–311)

The conception of the gods as Goethe cites it here corresponds to the consciousness that humans know themselves to be subject to beings who can arbitrarily determine their fate. In the *Parzenlied* (Song of the Fates), it is stated unmistakably in this regard that the gods can use their eternal rule as they please and that they avert their *segnendes Auge* (blessing eye) from entire generations.

In Greek myth, the gods punish Tantalus when he questions their power. Tantalus betrayed their trust and served them his slaughtered son, Pelops, to test their omniscience.¹⁴ In the mythical account of the relationship between Tantalus and the gods, as well as in the play's

¹⁴ In keeping with the sense of the mythical narrative, Goethe retained the guilt of Tantalus but softened it into an unspecified form of hubris by omitting the murder of his own son. According to Iphigenia and in the exact sense of the word, his offense was “human” (322), whereas this does not apply to offenses caused by the curse.

portrayal, the central issue is clearly power.¹⁵ However, when Tantalus transgressed against the gods in Goethe's interpretation, he was not yet under Jupiter's curse, so that his unspecified deed or deeds are not to be understood as a consequence of the curse. Only the curse irrevocably fixes the actions of the Tantalids on deceit and murder to give expression to the gods' claim to power and superiority.¹⁶

The myth reflects reality as struggles for power that also extend to the relationship between humans and gods. As the play as a whole reveals, in reality no curse existed or exists, nor is it needed to account for the behavior and actions of humans.

Even without a curse, humans act compulsively in line with the curse if Pylades's standpoint holds, a standpoint he attempts to transfer to Iphigenia in the fourth act and according to which it is necessity and the compulsion of circumstance that determine our actions:

You refuse in vain; Necessity commands
with iron hand, and her grave signal stands
As highest law, to which the gods themselves
are bound. The unadvised sister of eternal
Fate rules over us in silence. Bear, what she
Imposes; do, what she commands. (1680–86)

The mythical interpretation that attributes human action to the compulsion of a curse represents, in my view, a misinterpretation or, in Iphigenia's words, a misunderstanding. Goethe negates this interpretation and the mythical understanding of reality behind it. He demonstrates that no curse exists and that the destiny of humans is not determined by gods.¹⁷ If gods or a god do not exist, yet this notion is adopted as a foundation for a conception of reality based on faith, contradictions and paradoxes¹⁸ arise that conflict with modern consciousness and thinking.

¹⁵ See Blumenberg, 128: "Even the Olympian Zeus has traits of one who is resentful toward humans, of contempt toward those who are not his creatures, whom he had to take over from the Titans into his cosmos and whom he considers failed inhabitants of his world."; 129: "What has remained of Zeus's ill will toward humans is his inventiveness in entangling them in deadly struggles with one another." The well-known phrase regarding the "tremendous opposition in the background" of the play, from the 15th book of *Dichtung und Wahrheit*, refers to this problem of power; Goethe, *Werke: Hamburger Ausgabe*, ed. Erich Trunz (Munich: C.H. Beck, 1981) 10, 49.

¹⁶ Since Tantalus's actions were not determined by the curse, he is excluded from Orestes's reconciling projection. His culpable conduct stands as a symbol for the possibility of guilty action within the context of human strivings for power and human conflicts. The fact that Tantalus does not participate in the reconciliation speaks against Adorno's interpretation, according to which the madness monologue releases "the image of undiminished reconciliation." Theodor W. Adorno, "Zum Klassizismus von Goethes Iphigenie," *Neue Rundschau* 78 (1967): 596.

¹⁷ See, in contrast, the religious interpretation by Koch, according to whom the "events from beginning to end" are determined by the living agency of the gods; Friedrich Koch, "Die religiöse Grundstruktur von Goethes Iphigenie auf Tauris," in *Literatur und Geistesgeschichte: Festgabe für Heinz Otto Burger*, ed. Reinhold Grimm and Conrad Wiedemann (Berlin: De Gruyter, 1968), 151–61, 153.

¹⁸ Such contradictions and paradoxes are smoothed over in Brown and Stephens's presentation and integrated into an "economy of the mythical," which presupposes and prioritizes the mythical level as independently given and postulates a problematic "peculiar self-regulation" for it; see Kathryn Brown and Anthony Stephens: "Hinübergehen und unser Haus entschütten: Die Ökonomie des Mythischen in Goethes Iphigenie," *Jahrbuch der deutschen Schillergesellschaft* 32 (1988): 94–115. In this interpretation, mythical literalness is maintained without restriction

Within the framework of belief in gods, humans place themselves in a horizon of dependency that determines them from the outside. This creates ambiguity regarding the freedom available and due to them, and confines them in a way that deprives them of potential autonomy and freedom.

Faith and Action

In his critical examination of the mythical understanding of reality, Goethe brings into focus the relationship between the contents of consciousness and what is actually done. The text makes clear that no mythical curse determines human action and that believing it is a false and harmful conviction.

The crucial deed required by the curse would be for Iphigenia to kill Orestes and Pylades. However, this necessity is revealed, in relation to Orestes and following his healing, to be a false consciousness, and the act is ultimately avoided; for it is Iphigenia's intention from the outset not to incur blood-guilt—"O keep my hands from blood!" (549). Thoas, too, who could reinstate the old custom of human sacrifice and thereby execute the curse, refrains from doing so. The fact that humans can act in a way contrary to the curse disproves it.

In Goethe's work on myth, the validity of the assumption that mythically conceived powers influence human action is thus fundamentally relativized and decisively devalued in favor of autonomous action. The perspectival interest of the text is accordingly directed toward real events: the choices of the characters and the way they determine their personal and social destiny.

What characterizes all figures in the mythical context, however, is their reference to gods. This takes on different forms in each case, with the differences expressing how individuals reconcile their awareness of the gods with the realities and constraints at the level of action. The text consistently highlights the tension between mythic-ideological discourse and actual conduct.

The most central figure in relation to mythic-religious thought is Iphigenia, whose consciousness is strongly shaped by her faith. From the first scene on, however, it is emphasized that her interests and those of the goddess or the gods do not align. Iphigenia's belief differs from the heavily myth-based form that is negated in the text, since mythical objectification in her case is subjectivized through demythologization, this process taken so far that she reinterprets the gods in accordance with her own values.

The conflict of will between Iphigenia and the goddess Diana, which opens the play, has a real mythical foundation, as Iphigenia's sacrifice and rescue are understood as actual historical

and Orestes's healing is thus brought about by prayer, while at the end Iphigenia sets out in her role as priestess for the ritual expiation—understood as a cultic act—of her house. Regarding the concept of *Entsühnung* (expiation), see, by contrast, Dieter Borchmeyer, "Johann Wolfgang von Goethe: Iphigenie auf Tauris," *Deutsche Dramen: Interpretationen von der Aufklärung bis zur Gegenwart*, ed. Harro Müller-Michaels (Königstein/Ts.: Athenäum, 1985) 1:75: "In *Iphigenie*, the concept of expiation refers to the breaking of determination, of the causality of evil through Iphigenia's autonomous moral decision—through which she specifically does not succumb to evil, but steps out of the curse's sphere of influence."

events. It is Diana's "exalted will" that has kept Iphigenia hidden and preserved on Tauris for a long time; yet she only serves the goddess with "silent reluctance," as she refuses to resign herself to the fate that cast her upon Tauris. Insofar as the conflict of will is resolved by Iphigenia accomplishing her own rescue—the prerequisite being that Orestes is not sacrificed—the need for a renewed saving action by the goddess falls away: "And also save me, whom you saved from death, / From this life here." (52–53). The mythical dimension, if it is to be maintained, is thus restricted to a mythical discourse that interprets independent self-rescue as a rescue performed by the goddess or the gods.

That Iphigenia initially serves the goddess only with reluctance and disputes with the gods—her actions contradicting her own interpretation ("The gods I do not question, yet . . ." [23])—stems from the fact that it was the gods, as told by the myth, who first caused human misfortune through their dealings with humans. Iphigenia's actual situation is attributable to Diana's arbitrary act. While she knows that it was the goddess, her "savior," who had before demanded her as a sacrifice, she does not consider the implications of this demand for herself. In Iphigenia's account, the act is neutralized into the "strange curse" that struck her in Mycenae and separated her from her loved ones. In the course of this subjectivizing reinterpretation of the past, the goddess's arbitrary act, which lies behind the conflict of will, is overlooked. If it becomes possible in the play for Iphigenia to return to Mycenae and be reunited with some of her loved ones, then, strictly speaking, this only partially makes amends for the damage the gods caused within the mythical worldview when they cursed the human who challenged their power.

In addition to subjectivization, it is crucial for the preservation of Iphigenia's faith that she reinterprets the gods and adapts them to her own consciousness. In response to Thoas's demand to perform the sacrifice, Goethe has Iphigenia thus reply with a programmatic reference to the play's core problem of consciousness:

Gods do not lust for blood.
We misconstrue what they desire, to satisfy
Our own cruel drives. (523–25)

And she continues in the same vein, stating:

For the Immortals love the widespread
Good races of men,
And they gladly prolong the fleeting life
Of the mortal. (554–57)

The image Iphigenia projects of the gods in these words is diametrically opposed to their earlier actions and represents an Enlightenment-based¹⁹ correction of their mythical depiction. It is her

¹⁹ Rasch provides an excellent account of the "religious situation of the Enlightenment era" as it is reflected in the play. However, he defines the "central theme" too one-sidedly as "a religious" one. Rasch, *Goethes Iphigenie*, 8, 16.

own image of the gods that Iphigenia pleads to be preserved at the peak of her danger in the final scene of the fourth act. Her mythical speech objectifies the gods and postulates their intervention, yet her apostrophe serves only as a subjective expression of self-affirmation regarding the action she feels obligated to take:

The heavy hand of harsh necessity
 Now lays a double crime on me,
 To rob the sacred image of the goddess
 And deceive the man to whom I owe
 My life and destiny. Let me not turn
 Against the gods! I fear that in my heart
 The deep hatred the Titans felt
 For the Olympians is taking hold to claw
 And crush me. Save me, gods, and save
 Your image in my soul! (1707–717)

In these verses, Iphigenia can be subjectively in harmony with the invoked gods because she asks them—as a reflection of her inner image—only for what she herself is prepared to achieve and what she can reconcile with the demands of her heart as an authority independent of the gods.²⁰ She speaks mythically as if the gods were preserving their image, but she preserves her image of the gods herself by acting in accordance with the image in her soul.

There seems to be no reason to object to Iphigenia's subjective belief. However, the problematic nature of her theistic understanding becomes apparent when one considers that others invoke the same gods, confirming their own subjective interpretation of the divine will postulated by mythical tradition, yet drawing entirely different consequences.

Orestes and Pylades, for example, relate to religious concepts in a way that speaks against these. Pylades, in particular, who is “oriented toward a pragmatic worldly sense,”²¹ is depicted critically, as he strives to combine two irreconcilable forces. Pylades relies on his human cleverness and erroneously speculates that Diana yearns to leave the shores of the barbarians and that he and Orestes could serve as instruments of the divine will. He is guided by the false assumption that the words of the gods are not ambiguous and are therefore predictable. Yet this very error is disastrous, as hostile acts against Thoas (deceit and violence) would, in the given context, cause the curse to persist. Pylades’s problematic entanglement in myth unsettles and threatens Iphigenia in the independence she has found from it. Significantly, Orestes sends him away at the end of the penultimate scene (“wait quietly to see the end / The gods will find for us” [2025–26]), so that, like Tantalus, he is excluded from the reconciliation.

²⁰ See line 1648: “But still my own heart is not satisfied.”

²¹ Schmitz, *Kritische Gewaltenteilung*, 55.

Orestes, too, remains potentially ensnared in the curse. He recognizes only in hindsight, and as a kind of technical outcome,²² the “error” which blinded them: “Apollo has revealed our error. We see / Now how he veiled our eyes.” (2108–09)—in contrast to Iphigenia, who refused to heed the curse. Even in the final scene, Orestes is ready to make her freedom and the fate of all “strangers” dependent on the outcome of armed single combat—a misplaced display of bravery still in the spirit of the curse—whereupon once again only Iphigenia calls him to reason: “Don’t touch the sword! / Think of my fate!” (2065–66).

Yet Orestes precisely is not thinking of the fate of those affected by the curse when the goddess’s counsel finally appears as “beautiful and glorious” to him, because she had preserved Iphigenia in a sacred silence for the blessing of her brother and her kin. Just as his own fate—“They chose me to be the butcher, / To murder my revered mother” [707–08])—the bloody fate of Agamemnon and Clytemnestra also remains unconsidered. To him the goddess appears blameless as the wielder of power and the instigator of bloody horrors only because, in this way, his ideologizing justification is defamiliarized by the author.²³

If Orestes ultimately projects a one-sided mythical view in which the divine will is treated as absolute, this fundamentally contradicts the attitude and actions of Iphigenia and Thoas. In their first encounter (Act I, Scene 3), the insight is developed that the relationship to gods in individual experience is purely subjective in nature. Under pressure from Thoas to marry, Iphigenia thanks the gods for giving her “the firmness” not to enter into an alliance with him, which they (the gods) supposedly would not approve. This is followed by decisive and valid statements regarding the problem of any objective reference to the gods:

Thoas: You do not hear a god; your own heart speaks.

Iphigenia: Only our hearts can hear them. (493–94)

In his response, Thoas rejects Iphigenia's appeal to the gods, which seeks to justify her own convictions and to objectify the divine. He recognizes the ideological abuse inherent in this appeal; and Iphigenia sums up the subjective essence of religion in a concise statement: The gods speak to us only through our heart because their origin lies in the heart, when the heart is understood as the seat of our psychic nature.

²² "The fact that Orestes finds the correct interpretation of the oracle is meaningful, but not decisive for the outcome of the play. It is Iphigenia who has freed Orestes from the delusion that the gods intend his downfall. Since he has been helped without the oracle having to be followed literally, the prerequisite is established for him to interpret it correctly by inscribing the truth—offered on a concrete level—into the open mythical ambiguity. And again, it is Iphigenia who finally prevents the violent confrontation and brings about the peaceful solution. Seen in this light, Orestes does not have a “key function” at the end, and there is no “deus-ex-machina” solution with a resulting “weakness of motivation”; see Borchmeyer, “Iphigenie auf Tauris,” 70–71.

²³ In this sense, Koch's religiously oriented interpretation is completely unsatisfactory, according to which Orestes would “now be the carrier of a new blessed line” and would have “taken over the leadership”; see Koch, “Die religiöse Grundstruktur,” 154. Rasch correctly points out that the vision in Orestes's final speech is a perspectival one. However, Orestes is right about the role he ascribes to Iphigenia regarding his healing; see Rasch, *Goethe's Iphigenie*, 184–85.

Religious perception of gods is inherently subjective and thrives on the mediation and tradition of religious beliefs and customs. Thoas, too, is clearly the representative of a traditional religious practice, which he upholds until he finds compelling reasons to make changes. What leads him—contrary to mythically anchored custom—not to sacrifice Iphigenia, when she is cast away on the island, is his personal and very real interest in Iphigenia as a woman and thus also as a guarantor of an heir. Here, real interest prevails over mythically anchored custom as something more human. However, when Iphigenia does not comply with his wishes, he threatens to return to the old customs in order to make her submissive:

We should not seek to understand and to direct
The sacred usage with our fickle minds
According to our wishes.
Do your duty, and I will attend to mine. (528–31)

Unlike the rebellious Iphigenia, Thoas still wavers between tradition and the evolution of faith. That the more humane practice on Tauris arises from the pressure of real interests and is not derived from faith, and that, moreover, faith heteronomously determines action, points to the importance of engaging with myth, insofar as the ideological system has fallen behind social requirements and requires adaptation.

The Interest of the Other

Iphigenia succeeds in realizing her deep wish to return home and thus alters the fate that was imposed on her. Goethe conceived her as an exemplary figure whose actions stand in contrast to what is considered the norm. She acts exemplarily in the interest of others, defying the customs of an entire community in order to secure justice for others, and possesses the ability to convince others of the correctness of her viewpoint and actions, influencing them to align their behavior with her own.

Pylades is motivated in the completely opposite manner. From his perspective, deliberate action under the pressure of circumstances is directed toward the short-sighted advancement of one's own interests at the expense of others. If he proclaims his credo as an individual in the play, it is embodied on Tauris in a social system that defends against anything foreign to secure itself. Guided by her experience, however, Iphigenia decisively opposes this understanding—legitimized by tradition—which is based on fixed and established customs. Such customs embody the past and the status quo. They are firmly anchored in the consciousness of a community's members and are transmitted to descendants as ideologically fixed prescriptions.

The experience that has shaped Iphigenia is her experience of being a stranger. She is torn from the context of her family and separated from it. This experience, which shapes her consciousness, is for the present and the twentieth century in general a fundamental experience of displacement and exile. As an exile, Iphigenia has suffered a painful fate that she would have

wanted to avoid for herself and which she does not wish others to experience. A violent death, which she herself narrowly escaped at the last moment, is something she does not wish to inflict on others.

For this reason, she suspends the custom of sacrifice, even though it is sanctified by the cult of Diana. The play emphasizes that her humane behavior had a beneficial effect on the community in Tauris. If, therefore, barbaric human sacrifice was considered necessary and meaningful in the past so as not to endanger the community,²⁴ then this cruelty has lost its justification over the course of time.

What is practiced in Tauris as cruelty toward people in a social context is embodied in individual figures in the family history of the Tantalids. With her refusal and denial, Iphigenia refutes the necessity—entrenched in both social and individual consciousness—that the stranger or the neighbor must die as an enemy in the pursuit of one's own interests. This necessity is not a curse; it is only comparable to one. From the perspective of the play, it is inhuman; for it rests on a misjudgment of one's own broader interests and is the expression of an understanding of reality that does not do justice to human beings. Through Iphigenia, this is replaced, and a new way to act is postulated.

If Goethe demonstrates in the figure of Thoas that the required new form of action can also be realized in practice, the conditions under which he acts are decisive. For he, unlike Iphigenia, is not shaped by the experience of exile. As a ruler, he is one of the ruling class, whose actions are motivated by the necessity to maintain and strengthen power. In him, it must be shown whether the powerful are prepared to recognize the right of the weak stranger to self-determination. Thoas does exactly this: he heeds the voice of humanity, as he already did upon Iphigenia's arrival, when he committed to let her go should the possibility of a return home arise. Iphigenia knows that Thoas has the power to drag her by force from the altar to his bed (195–196), but she trusts him as a human being who adheres to justice and will therefore also respect her rights. What Thoas does is exemplary. He acts in contrast to Pylades's maxim of action and refutes it in principle:

Nor are humans called to judge themselves;
To go our way and see where we are going,
That is, what we are duty-bound to do:
For seldom do we know what we have done,
And what we do, we mostly fail to value. (1660–64)

Pylades's standpoint is that of ever-present self-interest. He is completely correct in asserting that we are not appointed to judge ourselves. We are appointed by no one and therefore are not cursed for our misdeeds. Yet the consequences of misdeeds act like a curse, and we are capable of judging ourselves for and deliberately avoiding them. This is possible for humans based on

²⁴ See lines 532–34: “Two strangers were discovered hiding / On the shore and have been captured. / They bring misfortune to our land.”

experience and insight. To act in the spirit of Iphigenia and correspondingly in the interest of the victims of tyranny and violence, to establish and uphold justice: this defines, within the play, the humanity that Iphigenia represents.²⁵

Thoas's exemplariness lies in the fact that he is capable not only of hearing the “voice of truth and humanity” but also of practicing it where he is required to set aside his own interest.²⁶ That he is willing to act humanely is crucially tied to and presupposes the concept of *truth*. Truth here is given a concrete form through a double right. Thoas recognizes, first, the legitimacy of Iphigenia's interests, and second, that he should not be deceived or cheated. In the context of the play, on the level of action, truth is the decisive concept underlying social conduct, as it establishes an objective category as the standard for determining justice, reaching understanding, and making value judgements.

The concept of truth is already introduced during the healing of Orestes as a central category related to the life-world and as a decisive prerequisite; for the healing begins with his confession and his demand for mutual truth—“let there be / Truth between us” (1080–81). Only where Orestes radically confronts the truth, does a change of consciousness become possible, and can the *Schwindel* (vertigo and deception) be removed from his brow,²⁷ the delusion that compelled him to matricide and let him experience the threatening fratricide as a certainty.

The practical significance of the category truth is then equally emphasized in the context of the events in the fifth act; for Iphigenia's late confession of the plot against Thoas represents a decisive precondition for resolving the conflict, since only in this way will the conflict not be decided by violence and will it not necessarily end with a bloody defeat for the Greeks, destroying all hope of return. Salvation lies solely with the counter-force to violence: truth. And although Iphigenia may appeal to the gods for this truth, she alone can implement it:

I strongly feel
A daring venture stir within me:
Bitter reproach will be my lot, deep

²⁵ An unclear image of this humanity impairs the presentation by Julie D. Prandi, in which the transfiguration of Iphigenia into a “beautiful soul” is rightly rejected while incorporating earlier criticism; see Prandi, “Goethe's Iphigenie as Woman,” *Germanic Review* 60 (1985): 23-31. Prandi limits the effect of Iphigenia's humanity to the private sphere, as she connects humanity with militant action and thus sees her excluded from the public sphere. The right to self-determination, however, which Iphigenia publicly claims and achieves for herself and all strangers, is a public right; in principle, it applies to all spheres. Iphigenia's humane actions also do not have their origin in “a kind of imprisonment, literally in the Diana temple and figuratively in the private sphere,” but in the experience of being a stranger, which is a public one; see 29.

²⁶ I cannot agree with Adorno's interpretation of Thoas's renunciation. According to Adorno, the play proposes that justice is realized through humanity, while an injustice is done to Thoas and he “is not allowed to participate in the highest humanity.” Thoas, however, is not a “disadvantaged party.” The renunciation is painful, but Thoas makes it because he recognizes it as the basis of law, and it is precisely through this act that he participates in the play's humanity (Adorno, 596). According to the text, Thoas is by no means left “internally shattered” nor does he “pay with the loss of his life's happiness.”

²⁷ See lines 750–53: “Then may a god take from my heavy brow / The torment that on this slippery path / Spattered with mother's blood / Draws me on to the dead.”

Misfortune will strike, should I fail or falter;
 But here I do reveal myself appealing to you!
 If you are true, as you are praised to be:
 Then show it by your aid and vindicate
 Truth through me! – Yes, hear me, O King! (1912–19)

After Iphigenia confesses to the planned attack, the further action in the fifth act consists of the suspension of violence followed by the verification of truth. Through public examination, it is ensured that indeed no deception is taking place. The understanding reached between the fighting parties ultimately results in Thoas's renunciation. As an action on the level of the present, this renunciation lies solely with Thoas, who also does not invoke the goddess or gods to justify it—in contrast to Orestes, who recognizes his error, but for whom this has no consequence in terms of his perception of reality.

Thoas and Iphigenia are the exemplary figures. Through them, fundamental principles for an equitable social order founded on law are projected.²⁸ At the conclusion, this order is represented by the “noble deed” of Thoas—his renunciation—, the hospitable guest-right established between both peoples, and, beyond that, a fundamental interest in the other’s well-being as an expression of “ancient friendship.”

The play is to be understood as a positive projection.²⁹ It teaches that law demands *Verzicht* (renunciation) if it is to be applied. Truth is only vindicated where humanity is practiced and the interests of the weaker party are acknowledged. In the view of the play, an improved and more humane practice can only be brought about if action is understood in its premises and consequences and by measuring the underlying ideological claims against the truth of praxis.

This is crucial. It is the power-protected and interest-driven myth, the theoretical systems and ideologies, that restrict law and legitimize inhumane practice. Meaningful work on myth means that ideological systems are measured against practice and that action which fails to prove its legitimacy is rejected. According to the play, what is false and destructive is the short-sighted self-interest that—as a matter of course—disregards the human right to life and self-determination, placing its own deadly interests above it.

Furthermore, the play shows that invoking gods cannot objectively compel them to act. Humans have created gods for themselves who still accompany them today. However, these gods have sprung from human consciousness and can therefore be made to serve human interests. Since invoked gods cannot speak audibly, everything depends on through which and through whose deeds they speak. Whoever is to receive a blessing for their deeds in the sense of the play

²⁸ Participation in this projected law-based order should be seen as desirable. It represents a freely chosen, non-negotiable form of rule and is, in this sense, free from guilt and the entanglement in the *Schuldzusammenhang des Lebendigen* (life’s continuum of guilt), which Adorno postulates for the *mündiges Subjekt* (autonomous agent) in the play (Adorno, 586).

²⁹ In the play, justice is served and the foundations for such justice are formulated. Goethe’s classicism is, therefore, more than a “cipher of the irreconcilable.” In my view, the notion that the intention of the play is to reconcile the irreconcilable cannot be inferred from it. See Adorno 591.

must, consequently, act blessedly themselves in order to partake in the blessing that Iphigenia bestows upon Thoas with her final wish:

The gods of generous deeds will bless you
For them! (2166–67)